

THE STATUS OF BULLYING CASES AND PREVENTION PRACTICES OF TEACHERS IN PRIVATE AND PUBLIC JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOLS IN THE THIRD CONGRESSIONAL DISTRICT OF QUEZON: BASIS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTERVENTION PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

In the Third Congressional District of Quezon, this study investigates the prevalence of bullying and prevention practices in Public and Private Junior High Schools. Research respondents in the study include guidance designate and junior high school teachers in both public and private schools. The descriptive research design was *used* in this study *since* it was the *best way to do* the investigation. The researcher *used* a self-designed questionnaire, modified from the work of another researcher, and based on pertinent legal underpinnings and literature. The two sections of the self-made questionnaire are separated. There are ten questions in the first section for each of the four categories of bullying—physical, verbal, emotional, and cyber. Information about the methods used by Guidance Counselors and Teachers to prevent bullying is gathered in the second section. Each respondent was given a short questionnaire through Google form or printed instrument. To answer the questions of the study, descriptive and inferential statistics were used. To determine the status of bullying in terms of the types and causes as well as the level of practices to prevent the occurrence of bullying cases, the weighted mean was utilized using a 4-point Likert scale presented in tables. However, the Mann-Whitney U test (t-test) was used to determine the significant difference in the severity of bullying between Private and Public Schools and the practices teachers and personnel used to prevent Bullying. The four types of bullying are rare and of low severity in Junior High Schools, both Public and Private. Bullying incidents may occasionally be influenced

by family, environment, and behavior, according to private junior high schools. There are significant differences in the severity of bullying cases between Private and Public Schools. The level of practices engaged by teachers and personnel to prevent the occurrence of bullying cases is high and lastly, there is no significant difference in the practices to prevent the occurrence of bullying cases between private and public schools. SECURE Program is used as an intervention program designed to address and prevent the slightly severe bullying cases in schools effectively.

Keywords: *Severity of Bullying, Private and Public Junior High Schools, Practices, Intervention Program*

INTRODUCTION

In a school setting, there are different problems students encounter and one of those is bullying. Many studies tried to address the problem, but unfortunately, those have been unsuccessful in resolving the issue. Since bullying occurs everywhere, whether in school premises or outdoors, there is a significant likelihood that the classroom instructor and guidance counselor may encounter this issue. Bullying, once seen by many as a necessary part of growing up, is now acknowledged as a serious, curable public health issue with potentially life-altering effects. (McDougall & Vaillancourt, 2015; Wolke & Lereya, 2015). These consequences for those who experienced bullying, for the perpetrators of bullying, and for witnesses who are present during a bullying event include poor school performance, anxiety, depression, and future delinquent and aggressive behavior. National and even local governments have responded by adopting laws and implementing programs to prevent Bullying and deal with its consequences. However, many of these responses have been made with little attention to what is known about bullying and its effects. Even the definition of bullying varies among both researchers and lawmakers. However, it generally includes physical and verbal behavior, behavior leading to social isolation, and behavior that uses digital communications technology (cyberbullying). This report adopts the term "bullying behavior," frequently used in research to cover all these behaviors.

Students who bully others are also more likely to continue bullying later in life and engage in risk-taking behaviors. Bullying has also been demonstrated to harm students who witness bullying as bystanders.

According to figures from the National Education Association (NEA), bullying is becoming more common monthly. An estimated 160,000 kids avoid school every day because they fear being attacked or intimidated by other classmates, which is considered Bullying. According to Dr. Noble (2010), a National Centre Against Bullying member who collaborates with the Federal Government on the National Safe Schools Framework, Bullying is a contentious issue. However, with effective communication of

the message that it is unacceptable, it is now more likely to be reported as being implemented in schools.

Some instances show how bullying occurs. In Asia-Pacific, the most common type of school bullying is verbal, e.g., 'being made fun of' or 'being called names' Chen (2015). A similar study in South America also finds verbal bullying as youngsters' most pervasive school bullying experience (Silva et al., 2013). Cyberbullying, though becoming controversial recently with several youth suicides, is less prevalent than traditional or face-to-face bullying (Modecki et al., 2014). Japan has reached at least 18% (Aoyama et al., 2012), the US at 17% (Bauman, 2012), while South Korea has reached at least 12% (Tippett & Kawk, 2012).

In the Philippines, 50 percent or one in every two Filipino school children is being bullied or abused in school (Ancho, 2013). Another consolidated statistic by the Department of Education reveals that bullying cases in the elementary and high schools of both private and public schools in 2014 rose by 21% or a total of 6,363 cases, compared to 5,236 in 2013. This number translates to 31 bullying cases daily from a divisor of 201 school days. These alarming statistics prompted the Department of Education (DepEd) to issue Department Order No. 40, s. 2012 entitled DepEd Child Protection Policy, whereby all elementary and secondary high schools in the country are to set up a system that will address bullying, discrimination, exploitation, violence, and other forms of abuse committed on the school premises. The Philippine Congress also enacted Republic Act 10627 (Anti-Bullying Law of 2013) to provide legal reinforcement to the department's initiatives in curbing the problem of Bullying and other related abuses in Philippine schools.

According to Koike (2011), in his study, students experienced physical, verbal, and social bullying very often. They are either physically attacked or hurt, verbally harassed or embarrassed in school by a student or a group of students and have experienced rumors or gossip spread about them. These experiences, the study noted, have an impact on the life and personality of the students. Hence, with Republic Act No. 10627, all elementary and secondary schools must adopt policies to prevent and address bullying. It requires further that if a bullying incident occurs, school counselors must adopt an intervention process to resolve the problem. (Austin, 2012).

Bullying is a very alarming issue among youngsters in and out of school, and the researcher takes an interest in this topic, notwithstanding the many problems that the next generation will encounter as consequences if the issue remains unsolved. The researcher finds it necessary for schools to have a well-developed prevention program for bullying accompanied by specific guidelines for implementation.

As an educator, the researcher believes that students should be provided with a safe, comfortable environment for learning. To create a safe environment where the students can thrive as learners, the researcher has decided to inquire into a phenomenon that often precludes students from thriving—bullying. It is the researcher's hope and intention that by learning more about the phenomenon of school bullying, she can take measures

to prevent bullying in her classroom. These preventative measures include fostering positive attitudes and empathy in her classroom to reduce the occurrence of bullying and teaching students coping strategies that they will use when they are bullied. A prevention program should also be adopted at different levels, whether individual level, classroom level, or social-wide level, to lessen the cases of bullying inside and outside school premises.

Research Questions

This study determined the status of bullying cases and prevention practices in the private and public junior high schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon as a basis for developing the Intervention Program.

Specifically, this tried to answer the following questions:

1. What is the status of severity of bullying cases in private and public schools in terms of:
 - 1.1 Types and Frequency of Occurrence;
 - 1.2 Severity;
 - 1.3 Causes?
 2. Is there a significant difference in the severity of bullying cases between private and public schools?
 3. What practices are employed by teachers and personnel to prevent the occurrence of bullying cases in:
 - 3.1. Private
 - 3.2. Public
 4. Is there a significant difference in the practices done by the teachers in private and public schools?
 5. What intervention Program for teachers and students could be developed to prevent Bullying cases?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher used the descriptive survey research design and employed a quantitative approach in gathering data. According to Calderon (2012), a descriptive research design is an intentional process of acquiring, analyzing, classifying, and tabulating information regarding current conditions, practices, beliefs, processes, trends, and cause-and-effect linkages and then providing a sufficient and accurate interpretation of that information, either with or without the use of additional sources of information.

The descriptive research method was utilized in this study for it is the most applicable method for the nature of the investigation.

The researcher believes this method could fully assist her in obtaining the facts about bullying incidents and the prevention measures relative to Bullying in Private and Public Junior High Schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon.

In this study, the researcher used the non-experimental mode of quantitative research in gathering data using a questionnaire administered to the target respondents.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in private and public junior high schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon. The researcher chose it because she knew that students are prone to bullying as she interviewed the school heads of both schools whether their students were experiencing bullying or not, most the schools in the Third District of Quezon before conducting the study. The researcher believes that these selected schools can provide more prosperous and more appropriate data for the attainment of the objectives of the study.

Quezon Province is included in the 81 Provinces in the entire Philippines. The combined land area of the provinces that make up the CALABARZON Region is 870,660 hectares. Quezon Province is in this region. It is the sixth-largest land area in the country and the largest in the region where the location is. Balesin Island is located in Palilio, Quezon. Villa Escudero is located in Tiaong; Kamay ni Hesus is found in Lucban, and Mount Banahaw is another popular tourist destination. There are several well-known tourist attractions in the province of Quezon. However, several new tourist destinations in the various municipalities are focused on farm tourism. There are seven (7) recognized farm tourism sites in Quezon Province, and four of them are in the municipality of Lucban. These sites are Samkara Restaurant and Garden Resort, Batis Aramin Resort and Hotel, Villa Elma, and Linang ni LK. The tourist office of Quezon province provided this information. Cortijo De Palsabangon in Pagbilao. Both Oyayi Farm and Resort in Sariaya and Yumi's Farm in Tayabas City are beautiful places to

visit. Quezon Province consists of four districts. The first district consists of the city of Tayabas and adjacent municipalities of Burdeos, General Nakar, Infanta, Jomalig, Lucban, Mauban, Pagbilao, Panukulan, Patnanungan, Polillo, Real and Sampaloc. It is currently represented in the 19th Congress by Wilfrido Mark M. Enverga of the Nationalist People's Coalition (NPC). The Second District consists of Quezon's capital city of Lucena and adjacent municipalities of Candelaria, Dolores, San Antonio, Sariaya, and Tiaong. It is currently represented in the 19th Congress by David C. Suarez of Lakas–CMD. Fourt District consists of municipalities in the Tayabas Isthmus and Alabat Island, namely Alabat, Atimonan, Calauag, Guinayangan, Gumaca, Lopez, Perez, Plaridel, Quezon, and Tagkawayan. It is currently represented in the 19th Congress by Keith Micah Tan of the Nationalist People's Coalition (NPC).

The Third Congressional District of Quezon, located in the province of Quezon, was formerly known as the Bondoc Peninsula, called initially Tayabas. Since 1987, it has had a member serving in the Philippine House of Representatives on its behalf. The district includes the municipalities of Agdangan, Buenavista, Catanauan, General Luna, Macalelon, Mulanay, Padre Burgos, Pitogo, San Andres, San Francisco, San Narciso, and Unisan. These municipalities are located on the Bondoc Peninsula, the southern portion of the Tayabas Isthmus, and the southwest shore of Ragay Gulf, respectively. Currently, it is being represented in the 19th Congress by Reynante Arrogancia of the Reporma, who joined the Nationalist People's Coalition later on. This position was assumed in July 2022.

Figure no. 1. Map of the Third Congressional District of Quezon Province
Source:intrepidwanderer.com

Research Population and Sample

The population frame of this study includes the guidance designate or guidance counselor and classroom teachers of public and private junior high schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon.

Out of 56 public junior high schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon, (12) schools were selected in each town through cluster sampling, utilized the fishbowl technique, and then randomly selected based on their categories, such as small, medium, and large schools. Ten (10) private schools in the Third Congressional District were also selected through purposive sampling.

Purposive sampling, also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling, is a non-probability sampling method that focuses on sampling techniques where the units are investigated based on the research judgment.

The target respondents of the study were Junior High School Teachers and designated guidance counselors in selected public and private Junior High Schools in the third congressional district of Quezon.

There were 426 teachers; however, during the data gathering, only 110 teachers' respondents participated in the study. The 110 teachers are composed of 48 teachers and 12 designated guidance counselors from Public Schools and 40 teachers and 10 designated guidance counselors from Private Schools.

Table No. 1

Number of Respondents from Public and Private Junior High Schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon.

Municipality	Public Schools	No. of Teacher	No. of Guidance Designates/ Guidance Counselor
Agdangan	Binagbag National High School	4	1
Buenavista	Buenavista National High School	4	1
Catanauan	San Jose National High School	4	1
General Luna	San Isidro National High School	4	1
Macalelon	Olongtao National High School	4	1
Mulanay	Ajos national High School	4	1
Padre Burgos	Lina Gayeta-Lasquety National High School	4	1
Pitogo	Sampalok National High School	4	1
San Andres	Camflora National High School	4	1
San Francisco	Renato Edaño Vicencio National High School	4	1
San Narciso	Abuyon National High School	4	1
Unisan	Unisan Integrated High School	4	1
Total 12		48	12

Municipality	Private Schools	No. of Teacher	No. of Guidance Designates/ Guidance Counselor
Buenavista	St. Lawrence Academy	4	1
Catanauan	Enverga University Inc.	4	1
General Luna	Saint Ignatius Parochial School	4	1
Macalelon	Macalelon High School	4	1
Mulanay	St. Peter Catholic School of Mulanay	4	1
Padre Burgos	Holy Cross Academy	4	1
Pitogo	Western Tayabas High School	4	1
San Francisco	Bondoc Peninsula Institute Inc.	4	1
San Narciso	St. Joseph High School	4	1
Unisan	Dominican Academy	4	1
Total 10		40	10

Research Instrument

The researcher utilized a self-designed questionnaire grounded on relevant literature and legal foundations. The self-made Questionnaire is divided into two parts. The initial section involves identifying the types and Frequency of bullying incidents in the school and the perceived causes of Bullying. The first part consists of four types of Bullying namely physical, verbal, emotional, and cyber bullying having ten questions in each type. The second section involves gathering information on the practices of teachers and guidance counselors in preventing Bullying, having ten questions. It was presented first to the research adviser for comments, suggestions, and validation. Corrections on the content and structure, comments, and suggestions from the validators were considered and applied to the final copy of the Questionnaire.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought permission from the superintendent, supervisor, and principal through a letter of request noted by her research adviser and deans of graduate studies from Marinduque State College and Quezonian Educational College, Inc. to conduct and retrieve the survey. Each respondent was given a short questionnaire through Google

form or printed instrument based on the respondent's preference so that answering the instrument took little of their time. They were oriented on the flow of the research and discussed the Data Privacy Act to convince them to answer the research instrument. The respondents will confirm the data gathered through Google Forms and printed instruments so that the researcher can use the respondents' data.

The researcher applied statistical tools to get the exact figure of responses through the statistician's help to answer the research questions.

The researcher used a 4-point Likert Scale to know the status of bullying incidents in terms of the types of bullying cases and the perceived causes.

Likert Scale for the Types and Frequency of Bullying

Scale	Mean Interval	Verbal Interpretation	Qualitative Description
4	3.25-4.00	Always	The frequency of the types of bullying can always be seen.
3	2.50-3.24	Sometimes	The frequency of the types of bullying can often be seen.
2	1.75-2.49	Seldom	The frequency of the types of bullying can rarely be seen.
1	1.00-1.74	Never	The frequency of the types of bullying can never be seen.

Likert Scale for the Severity of Bullying

Scale	Mean Interval	Verbal Interpretation	Qualitative Description
4	3.25-4.00	Highly Severe	The severity of bullying can always be seen.
3	2.50-3.24	Severe	The severity of bullying can often be seen.
2	1.75-2.49	Slightly Severe	The severity of bullying can rarely be seen.
1	1.00-1.74	Not Severe	The severity of bullying can never be seen.

Likert Scale for the Causes of Bullying

Scale	Mean Interval	Verbal Interpretation	Qualitative Description
4	3.25-4.00	Always	The causes of bullying can always be seen.
3	2.50-3.24	Sometimes	The causes of bullying can often be seen.
2	1.75-2.49	Seldom	The causes of bullying can rarely be seen.
1	1.00-1.74	Never	The causes of bullying can never be seen.

Likert Scale for Practices of Teachers

Scale	Mean Interval	Verbal Interpretation	Qualitative Description
4	3.25-4.00	Always	The practices of teachers can always be seen.
3	2.50-3.24	Sometimes	The practices of teachers can often be seen.
2	1.75-2.49	Seldom	The practices of teachers can rarely be seen.
1	1.00-1.74	Never	The practices of teachers can never be seen.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To answer the questions of the study, descriptive and inferential statistics were used. To determine the status of bullying in terms of the types and causes as well as the level of practices to prevent the occurrence of bullying cases, the **weighted** mean was utilized using a 4-point Likert scale presented in tables. However, the **Mann-Whitney U test (t-test)** was used to determine the significant difference in the severity of bullying between private and public schools and the practices teachers and personnel used to prevent Bullying.

RESULTS

Part I. Status of Bullying

Table 2

*Types and Frequency of Occurrence of Physical, Verbal, Emotional and Cyber Bullying Cases in Selected **Private** and **Public** Junior High Schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon*

Physical Bullying	Private		Public		Combined Mean	
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	DI
1. Student hits someone without a cause	2.55	Som	2.06	S	2.31	S
2. Student kicks another student	2.35	S	2.00	S	2.18	S
3. Student push someone in the hallway	2.60	Som	2.06	S	2.33	S
4. Student pushes someone while playing	2.38	S	2.09	S	2.24	S
5. Student tears cloth of her/his classmate.	1.50	N	1.38	N	1.44	N
6. Student start chaos to someone while playing	2.28	S	1.78	S	2.03	S
7. Student eyeing someone that looks weaker	2.28	S	2.01	S	2.15	S
8. Student pinches someone who does no harm to her/him	1.95	S	1.84	S	1.90	S
9. Student blocks someone to show that he/she is strong.	2.10	S	1.76	S	1.93	S
10. Student touches in unwanted and inappropriate ways.	1.98	S	1.78	S	1.88	S
Composite Mean	2.20	S	1.88	S	2.04	S

Verbal Bullying	Private		Public		Combined Mean	
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	DI
1. Name calling someone in an inappropriate manner.	2.53	Som	2.28	S	2.41	S
2. Mocking another student.	2.28	S	2.21	S	2.25	S
3. Teasing his/her classmate.	2.43	S	2.44	S	2.44	S

4. Pointing at the same time laughing at other student.	2.38	S	2.03	S	2.21	S
5. Making bad comments.	2.30	S	2.12	S	2.21	S
6. Taunting another student with insulting remarks.	2.23	S	1.94	S	2.09	S
7. Degrading the ability of his/her classmates.	2.18	S	1.87	S	2.03	S
8. Insulting another student by their physical appearance.	2.25	S	1.90	S	2.08	S
9. Giving disrespectful comments toward others.	2.13	S	2.14	S	2.14	S
10. Shouting at another student to get attention.	2.28	S	2.29	S	2.29	S
Composite Mean	2.30	S	2.12	S	2.21	S

Emotional Bullying	Private		Public		Combined Mean	
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	DI
1. Threatening someone to get what he/she wants.	2.18	S	1.65	N	1.92	S
2. Manipulating other student during vacant period.	2.18	S	1.72	S	1.95	S
3. Blackmailing other student to do what he/she wants him to do.	1.83	S	1.60	N	1.72	N
4. Making faces at someone intentionally	2.00	S	1.91	S	1.96	S
5. Excluding other student during group activities.	2.03	S	1.85	S	1.94	S
6. Manipulating friendship by rejecting	1.93	S	1.60	N	1.77	S
7. Ignoring other students	1.85	S	1.93	S	1.89	S
8. Talking behind one's back	2.03	S	2.09	S	2.06	S
9. Accusing others falsely	1.88	S	2.03	S	1.96	S
10. Preventing someone from joining or being part of a group.	1.75	S	1.91	S	1.83	S
Composite Mean	1.97	S	1.83	S	1.90	S

Cyberbullying	Private		Public		Combined Mean	
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	DI
1. Using text messaging to threaten the target.	1.63	N	1.53	N	1.58	N
2. Posting embarrassing information on social networking sites such as Facebook.	1.58	N	1.62	N	1.60	N
3. Participating in text wars or text attacks, which occur when bullies gang up on the victim and send thousands of texts.	1.60	N	1.38	N	1.49	N
4. Setting up an account on a social networking site and posting as the victim while saying mean, hurtful or offensive things online.	1.35	N	1.38	N	1.37	N
5. Threatening to share embarrassing photos as a way of blackmailing the victim	1.60	N	1.37	N	1.49	N
6. Posting insulting comments about the victim via the chat option of online gaming sites.	1.48	N	1.44	N	1.46	N
7. Using a camera phone to video and later share a bullying incident, which may include one or more kids slapping, hitting, kicking or punching the victim	1.33	N	1.44	N	1.39	N
8. Sharing a video via mass e-mail or text messaging to humiliate the victim.	1.38	N	1.31	N	1.35	N
9. Posting tweets or Facebook posts that never mention the victim's name.	1.53	N	1.58	N	1.56	N
10. Spreading <u>rumors</u> about the victim online through websites or blogs.	1.60	N	1.41	N	1.51	N
Composite Mean	1.51	N	1.45	N	1.48	N
Grand Mean	2.00	S	1.82	S	2.00	S

Legend:

3.25 – 4.00 Always (A)
 2.50 – 3.24 Sometimes (Som)
 1.75 – 2.49 Seldom (S)
 1.00 – 1.74 Never (N)

Descriptive Interpretation (DI)

Table 3

The severity of Physical, Verbal, Emotional and Cyberbullying Cases in Selected Private and Public Junior High Schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon

	Private		Public		Combined Mean	
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	DI
Physical Bullying						
1. Student hits someone without a cause	2.20	SS	1.71	NS	1.96	SS
2. Student kicks another student	2.25	SS	1.65	NS	1.95	SS
3. Student push someone in the hallway	2.35	SS	1.59	NS	1.97	SS
4. Student pushes someone while playing	2.10	SS	1.66	NS	1.88	SS
5. Student tears cloth of her/his classmate.	1.55	NS	1.37	NS	1.46	NS
6. Student start chaos to someone while playing	2.08	SS	1.69	NS	1.89	SS
7. Student eyeing someone that looks weaker	2.03	SS	1.53	NS	1.78	SS
8. Student pinches someone who does no harm to her/him	2.20	SS	1.50	NS	1.85	SS
9. Student blocks someone to show that he/she is strong.	2.15	SS	1.54	NS	1.85	SS
10. Student touches in unwanted and inappropriate ways.	1.80	SS	1.60	NS	1.70	NS
Composite Mean	2.10	SS	1.58	NS	1.83	SS

	Private		Public		Combined Mean	
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	DI
Verbal Bullying						
1. Name calling someone in an inappropriate manner.	2.40	SS	1.85	SS	2.13	SS
2. Mocking another student.	2.33	SS	1.78	SS	2.06	SS
3. Teasing his/her classmate.	2.38	SS	1.85	SS	2.12	SS
4. Pointing at the same time laughing at other student.	2.15	SS	1.62	NS	1.89	SS
5. Making bad comments.	2.43	SS	1.75	SS	2.09	SS
6. Taunting another student with insulting remarks.	2.13	SS	1.68	NS	1.91	SS
7. Degrading the ability of his/her classmates.	2.13	SS	1.59	NS	1.86	SS
8. Insulting another student by their physical appearance.	2.08	SS	1.60	NS	1.84	SS
9. Giving disrespectful comments toward others.	2.15	SS	1.69	NS	1.92	SS
10. Shouting at another student to get attention.	2.15	SS	1.68	NS	1.92	SS
Composite Mean	2.23	SS	1.71	NS	1.97	SS

	Private		Public		Combined Mean	
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	DI
Emotional Bullying						
1. Threatening someone to get what he/she wants.	2.20	SS	1.60	NS	1.90	SS
2. Manipulating other student during vacant period.	1.98	SS	1.49	NS	1.74	NS
3. Blackmailing other student to do what he/she wants him to do.	1.68	NS	1.43	NS	1.56	NS
4. Making faces at someone intentionally	2.00	SS	1.56	NS	1.78	SS
5. Excluding other student during group activities.	1.95	SS	1.44	NS	1.70	NS
6. Manipulating friendship by rejecting	1.80	SS	1.32	NS	1.56	NS
7. Ignoring other students	2.13	SS	1.57	NS	1.85	SS
8. Talking behind one's back	2.20	SS	1.72	NS	1.96	SS
9. Accusing others falsely	1.85	SS	1.63	NS	1.74	NS
10. Preventing someone from joining or being part of a group.	1.95	SS	1.72	NS	1.84	SS
Composite Mean	1.97	SS	1.55	NS	1.76	SS

Cyberbullying	Private		Public		Combined Mean	
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	DI
1. Using text messaging to threaten the target.	1.68	NS	1.60	NS	1.64	NS
2. Posting embarrassing information on social networking sites such as Facebook.	1.63	NS	1.49	NS	1.56	NS
3. Participating in text wars or text attacks, which occur when bullies gang up on the victim and send thousands of texts.	1.50	NS	1.43	NS	1.47	NS
4. Setting up an account on a social networking site and posting as the victim while saying mean, hurtful or offensive things online.	1.35	NS	1.56	NS	1.46	NS
5. Threatening to share embarrassing photos as a way of blackmailing the victim	1.58	NS	1.44	NS	1.51	NS
6. Posting insulting comments about the victim via the chat option of online gaming sites.	1.40	NS	1.32	NS	1.36	NS
7. Using a camera phone to video and later share a bullying incident, which may include one or more kids slapping, hitting, kicking or punching the victim	1.25	NS	1.57	NS	1.41	NS
8. Sharing a video via mass e-mail or text messaging to humiliate the victim.	1.58	NS	1.72	NS	1.65	NS
9. Posting tweets or Facebook posts that never mention the victim's name.	1.65	NS	1.55	NS	1.60	NS
10. Spreading <u>rumors</u> about the victim online through websites or blogs.	1.68	NS	1.41	NS	1.55	NS
Composite Mean	1.53	NS	1.51	NS	1.52	NS
Grand Mean	2.00	SS	1.60	NS	1.77	SS

Legend:

3.25 – 4.00 *Highly Severe (HS)*
2.50 – 3.24 *Severe (SS)*
1.75 – 2.49 *Slightly Severe (SS)*
1.00 – 1.74 *Not Severe (NS)*

Descriptive Interpretation (DI)

Table 4

*Perceived Causes of Bullying Incidents in Selected **Private** and **Public** Junior High Schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon*

Indicators	Private		Public		Combined Mean	
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	DI
A. Behavior and Attitude						
1. Aggression	2.48	S	2.12	S	2.30	S
2. want to become powerful over another	2.53	Som	2.06	S	2.30	S
3. want to hurt others	2.60	Som	1.90	S	2.25	S
4. want to be recognized	2.93	Som	2.18	S	2.56	Som
5. just for fun	2.90	Som	2.49	S	2.70	Som
Composite Mean	2.69	Som	2.15	S	2.42	S
B. Family						
1. Lack of love and attention from family	2.95	Som	2.72	Som	2.84	Som
2. Harsh discipline by parents	2.80	Som	2.46	S	2.63	Som
3. Broken Family	3.03	Som	2.75	Som	2.89	Som
4. Parental Rejection	2.83	Som	2.47	S	2.65	Som
5. Lack of Supervision	2.95	Som	2.57	Som	2.76	Som
Composite Mean	2.91	Som	2.59	Som	2.75	Som
C. Environment						
1. Lack of supervision from teachers	1.98	S	1.78	S	1.88	S
2. Observation from the environment	2.43	S	2.13	S	2.28	S
3. Peer Rejections	2.58	Som	1.94	S	2.26	S
4. Provocation	2.60	Som	2.01	S	2.31	S
5. Acts seeking Attention	2.65	Som	2.16	S	2.41	S
Composite Mean	2.45	S	2.00	S	2.23	S
Grand Mean	2.68	Som	2.25	S	2.47	S

Legend:

3.25 – 4.00	Always (A)	<i>Descriptive Interpretation (DI)</i>
2.50 – 3.24	Sometimes (Som)	
1.75 – 2.49	Seldom (S)	
1.00 – 1.74	Never (N)	

Part II. The significant difference in Bullying Cases between Private and Public Junior High Schools

Table 5

Statistical Tables Showing the Significant Difference in Severity of Bullying Cases between Private and Public Junior High Schools

Grouping Variable	Test variables	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
School Category (Private& Public)	Severity	.001	Significant	Reject Ho

Part III. Practices Employed by teachers and personnel to prevent the occurrence of Bullying

Table 6

*Practices Employed by the Respondents to Prevent Bullying in Selected **Private** and **Public** Junior High Schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon.*

Indicators	Private		Public		Combined Mean	
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI	Mean	DI
1. Counseling helps you to make practical decisions about how to deal with the bullying situation.	3.43	Always	3.72	Always	3.58	Always
2. Emphasizing bullying prevention during Parents-Teachers Association meetings.	3.53	Always	3.60	Always	3.57	Always
3. Implement evidenced-based bullying prevention programs and social-emotional learning programs.	3.38	Always	3.26	Always	3.32	Always
4. Provide opportunities to practice pro-social behavior.	3.33	Always	3.32	Always	3.33	Always
5. Conform to principles of child protection and positive and non-violent discipline	3.43	Always	3.56	Always	3.50	Always
6. Help the victim, the bully, and the bystanders understand the bullying incident and its negative consequences	3.50	Always	3.60	Always	3.55	Always
7. Periodic assessment and monitoring of the nature, extent, and perceptions of bullying behaviors and attitudes of students	3.38	Always	3.24	Som	3.31	Always
8. Continue personnel training, workshop and seminars to sustain bullying prevention programs	3.35	Always	3.18	Som	3.27	Always
9. Portray positive school climate and environment conducive to the attainment of learning objectives, the development of healthy relationships and the understanding of and respect for individual differences	3.30	Always	3.43	Always	3.37	Always

10. Coordination with Local Government Units, barangay (Barangay Council for the Protection of Children) and other stakeholders	3.25	Always	3.46	Always	3.36	Always
Grand Mean	3.39	Always	3.44	Always	3.42	Always

Legend:

3.25 – 4.00	Always (A)	<i>Descriptive Interpretation (DI)</i>
2.50 – 3.24	Sometimes (Som)	
1.75 – 2.49	Seldom (S)	
1.00 – 1.74	Never (N)	

Part IV. Level of Practices

Table 7

Statistical Tables Showing the Significant Difference in Practices to Prevent the Occurrence of Bullying Cases between Private and Public Junior High Schools.

Grouping Variable	Test variables	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
School Category (Private & Public)	Practices	.879	Not Significant	Do not reject Ho

DISCUSSION

Part I. Status of Bullying

Table 2 shows that Physical Bullying incidents in both private and public Junior High Schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon is categorized as "seldom" to "sometimes." The mean scores for most indicators manifest that physical bullying occurs occasionally but not frequently. The indicators with the highest mean scores include students hitting someone without a cause, pushing someone in the hallway, starting chaos while playing, and eyeing someone who appears weaker. These behaviors are more prevalent in private schools compared to public schools. However, it is important to note that the overall grand mean for physical bullying incidents in both private and public schools falls within the "seldom" category. Addressing and preventing physical bullying through proactive measures, such as implementing anti-bullying programs and

promoting a positive school climate, can contribute to creating safer environments for students in Junior High Schools.

This suggests that even though there is very little incidence of physical bullying in both private and public junior high schools, it is very possible for there to be incidents of hitting someone without provocation, shoving someone while playing, and pushing someone in the corridor. The outcome of the study is consistent with Bueno's statement from 2019, which stated that bullying is defined as "a severe repeated act that causes fear of physical, emotional, or property damage; unwanted physical interaction between the aggressor and the target, such as striking, pushing, shoving, kicking, slapping, tickling, headlocks; perpetrating school pranks; taunting;

This table shows the frequency of Verbal Bullying incidents in both Private and Public Junior High Schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon is categorized as "seldom." The mean scores for most indicators indicate that verbal bullying occurs occasionally but not frequently. The indicators with the highest mean scores include name-calling inappropriately, mocking another student, and teasing classmates. These behaviors are slightly more prevalent in private schools compared to public schools. However, overall, the grand mean for verbal bullying incidents in both private and public schools falls within the "seldom" category. It is important to address and prevent verbal bullying by promoting respectful communication and fostering a positive and inclusive school environment.

This suggests that incidents of Verbal Bullying are uncommon in both Private and Public Junior High Schools; however, it is quite likely that students will use inappropriate language when referring to other students and scream at them to get their attention. This result is relative to the statement of Bueno (2019) where any defamatory statement or allegation that causes the victim excessive emotional distress, such as directing foul language or obscenities at the target, calling the victim names, torturing them, and commenting unfavorably on the victim's appearance, clothing, or body was a kind of bullying that arise in school.

Also, it demonstrates that the frequency of Emotional Bullying incidents in both Private and Public Junior High Schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon is categorized as "seldom." The mean scores for most indicators indicate that emotional bullying occurs occasionally but not frequently. Threatening someone to get what they want and manipulating other students during vacant periods were found to be more prevalent in private schools compared to public schools. However, overall, the grand mean for emotional bullying incidents in both private and public schools falls within the "seldom" category. It is essential to address and prevent emotional bullying by promoting empathy, fostering positive relationships, and teaching conflict resolution skills.

The frequency with which incidents of emotional bullying occurred in private and public high schools can be inferred from this information to be low. On the other hand, talking about someone behind their back, making faces at someone, making false allegations against other people, and influencing other students during leisure time are all things that are likely to happen.

This finding is relevant to the research conducted by Schofield (2011), who found that the most common form of bullying is emotional assault. In some moments in their lives, more than half of all individuals will, at some point or another, be subjected to this form of torment.

The data presented in Table 2 indicate that a Cyberbullying incident never happened in both Private and Public Junior High Schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon. This could mean that the students never engage in behaviors such as using text messaging to threaten others, posting embarrassing information on social networking sites, or participating in text wars or text attacks. Additionally, sharing mean or offensive content online, using camera phones to record bullying incidents, and spreading rumors about victims online are infrequent occurrences. The grand mean for cyberbullying incidents in both private and public schools falls within the "never" category, indicating a low prevalence of cyberbullying. It is important to continue promoting a safe and respectful online environment for students.

This suggests that abuse in junior high schools, whether private or public, is unlikely to occur. However, students can threaten targets via text texts, share embarrassing information on social media, and tweet or post without naming the victim. As a direct result of this study shows support to the finding of Sbarbaro & Enyeart-Smith, (2011) where cyberbullying has developed into an increasingly widespread occurrence. Students are now able to engage in constant bullying of their classmates as a direct result of the quick development of technology. Text messages, e-mails, and websites that allow for the simple and quick dissemination of negative material can all be considered forms of cyberbullying that can be used to harass another person.

The types and frequency of occurrence of physical, verbal, emotional, and cyber bullying in selected private and public junior high schools got the total grand mean of 2.00 which was verbally interpreted as seldom.

Based on the data shown in Table 3, Physical Bullying incidents are assessed as slightly severe in both types of schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon. Students in both Private and Public schools are slightly engaged in hitting without cause, kicking, pushing in the hallway, pushing while playing, starting chaos during play, eyeing weaker individuals, pinching without provocation, blocking others to show strength, and engaging in unwanted and inappropriate touching.

This suggests that there is a less prevalent problem with Physical Bullying in both Private and Public Junior High Schools; however, students who shove someone in the hallway, punch someone without justification, and kick another student may likely cause severe incidents to occur. These findings of the study could be related to the findings of Raskauskas & Modell (2011), who found out that bullying could involve actions like physical violence, threats, quips or language, or criticizing someone's appearance. All these variables can have an individual impact or work in concert to contribute to a child's involvement in bullying. Because of these factors, bullying has been recognized as one of the most significant health hazards for children and one of the most prevalent problems that children experience in the educational system.

As reflected in Table 3, Verbal Bullying incidents are slightly severe in Private Schools and not severe in Public Schools. Students in both Private and Public Schools engage in incidents such as name-calling, mocking, teasing, pointing and laughing, making bad comments, taunting with insulting remarks, degrading classmates' abilities, insulting physical appearance, giving disrespectful comments, and shouting for attention of different levels of severity.

This implies that instances of Verbal Bullying in Private and Public Junior High Schools are slightly serious even though appropriate name-calling, picking on a peer, and making derogatory comments are likely to occur at any moment. The result of the findings is relative to the findings of Koike (2011) who found out that students are frequently subjected to bullying of various forms, including verbal bullying. Students' lives and personalities are impacted when they are the target of bullying at school, whether it takes the form of being physically assaulted or injured, being verbally harassed or embarrassed, or being the subject of embarrassing stories or slander shared about them.

The data in Table 3 indicate in the selected Private and Public Junior High Schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon, Emotional Bullying incidents are assessed as slightly severe in Private Schools and not severe in Public Schools. Students in both private and public schools engage in incidents such as threatening to get what they want, manipulating others, blackmailing, making faces intentionally, excluding peers during group activities, manipulating friendships by rejecting, ignoring others, talking behind someone's back, accusing others falsely, and preventing someone from joining or being part of a group.

This shows that there are slightly more emotional incidents in Private Schools than in Public Schools. The result was related to the statement that bullying, as a form of psychological or physical maltreatment, according to Storey and Slaby (2013), an abuser deliberately injures someone and does so to do so, chooses the same victim frequently, and has a power disparity, which means bullies choose people they think are weaker or more vulnerable. Moreover, the result supports Schofield's (2011) finding that the most common form of bullying is emotional assault.

As presented in Table 3, Cyberbullying incidents are assessed as not severe in both Private and Public Schools. Students in both types of schools engage in incidents such as using text messaging to threaten, posting embarrassing information on social networking sites, participating in text wars or attacks, pretending to be the victim and posting offensive content, threatening to share embarrassing photos, posting insulting comments on online gaming sites, using a camera phone to record and share bullying incidents, sharing humiliating videos via email or text messaging, posting tweets or Facebook posts indirectly targeting the victim, and spreading rumors online through websites or blogs.

This implies that emotional bullying incidents are slightly serious for both Private and Public Junior High Schools although preventing someone from entering or being a member of a group and threatening might severely occur. These results were similar to

the findings of Lines (2008), where one person or a group of people intimidate another person in any way, whether physically, socially, mentally, or emotionally, this behavior is referred to as bullying. It can also refer to the act of hitting someone or calling them names, both of which are likely to make the other person furious, wounded, or agitated.

The severity of physical, verbal, emotional, and cyberbullying incidents in selected private and public junior high schools got a total grand mean of 1.77 which was verbally interpreted as slightly severe.

Table 4 presents the details of causes that led to instances of Bullying in both Private and Public Junior High Schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon. The perceived causes of bullying incidents can be categorized into three main areas: behavior and attitude, family, and environment. As regards behavior and attitude, factors such as aggression, a desire to become powerful over others, a desire to hurt others, a desire to be recognized, and engaging in bullying just for fun were identified. These factors were perceived to occur sometimes, with a composite mean in private schools and public schools. In the family domain, factors such as a lack of love and attention from family, harsh discipline by parents, coming from broken families, parental rejection, and a lack of supervision were mentioned. These family-related factors were also perceived to occur sometimes, with a composite mean in private schools and public schools. In the environmental context, factors such as a lack of supervision from teachers, observation from the environment, peer rejections, provocation, and acts seeking attention were identified. These environmental factors were perceived to occur sometimes, with a composite mean in private schools and public schools. The overall grand mean for all perceived causes of bullying incidents in private schools and public schools indicates that these causes were perceived to occur sometimes in both settings.

This implies that the primary reason students for both Private and Public Junior High Schools tend to bully one another is because of their relationships with their families. This result is related to the finding of Olweus (1980) where children acquire their personalities and values from their families. There is a linked a boy's aggression to his mother's negativity, permissiveness, and power-aggressive punishment. This supports the idea that unhappy families can breed violent children. Children who are disciplined by violence, animosity, and control learn aggression, rebellion, and fear. Non-permissive parenting would calm preschoolers.

Part II. The significant difference of Bullying Cases between Private and Public Junior High Schools

Emotional Bullying in private schools got a composite mean of 1.97 "Slightly Severe" in public schools got 1.55 "Not Severe" and the combined mean was 1.76 " Slightly Severe". The last type of bullying cases is cyberbullying. The private schools got a mean of 1.53 "Not Severe" and the public schools got 1.51 "Not Severe". The combined mean is 1.52 "Not Severe"

The Grand mean of the Four types of bullying in private schools was 2.00 which was verbally interpreted as "Slightly Severe" while in public schools got the grand mean of

1.60 which was verbally interpreted as “Not Severe”. The combined grand mean of the two Junior high Schools is 1.77 which was verbally interpreted as “Slightly Severe”.

This suggests that there are differences in the severity of bullying that happens in both private and public settings as bullying was more severe in private rather than public schools.

This finding is in contrast with the study of Tippett and Wolke (2014) stated that the likelihood of becoming a victim or bully victim increases with low Socioeconomic status (SES), and the early children from low-income families may have experienced things that contributed toward the potential for victimization. This study suggested that the likelihood of becoming either a victim of bullying or a bully victim (someone who is both a perpetrator and a victim of bullying) is higher among children from lower socioeconomic backgrounds. The reasoning provided by Tippett and Wolke is that children from lower-income families might experience environmental or familial conditions that predispose them to be involved in bullying, either as victims or perpetrators.

This also suggests that bullying is a multifaceted issue and might be influenced by a variety of factors, including but not limited to SES. The nature of bullying in private schools may involve more relational or psychological aggression due to cultural pressures about status and achievement, whereas in public schools or among lower SES groups, bullying might manifest in different ways, possibly more physical or overt due to different environmental stresses.

Part III. Practices Employed by teachers and personnel to prevent the occurrence of Bullying

Table 6 shows the detailed practices employed to prevent bullying in selected private and public Junior High Schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon. The mean score across the board was 3.42, which could be understood that the schools investigated always have preventive practices to control bullying cases.

The combined means for practices employed in Private and Public Junior High Schools emphasizes the first indicator, counseling helping you to make practical decisions about how to deal with the bullying situation with a mean value of 3.58. The second indicator emphasized bullying prevention during Parents-Teachers Association meetings with a mean of 3.57. The third indicator conforms to principles of child protection and positive and non-violent discipline with a mean of 3.50.

This indicates that teachers in Private and Public Junior High Schools take into consideration the possibility of students receiving counseling as a means of assisting students in arriving at actionable decisions regarding how to respond to the bullying situation, emphasize the prevention of bullying with parents and teachers assist the victim, the bully, and bystanders in comprehending the bullying occurrence and its negative effects. The result is relative to the result of Hinduja & Patchin, (2013) where their result said that teachers have a big part to play in stopping bullying, which is now

seen as a major problem in schools. Bullying is still talked about a lot in the news, which shows how much people care about it and how much anti-bullying work is needed in schools (Mavroveli & Sánchez-Ruiz, 2011).

Part IV. Level of Practices

Table 7 shows that there is no significant difference on the practices to prevent the occurrence of bullying cases between Private and Public Junior High Schools ($p = .879 > 0.05$).

Therefore, the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the level of practices done by teachers and personnel to prevent the occurrence of bullying was **accepted**. The grand mean for the level of practices employed by the teachers in private schools got 3.39 interpreted as “Always” while public schools got the grand mean of 3.44 verbally interpreted as “Always”. The combined mean for this table is 3.42 verbally interpreted as “Always”.

Despite these differences in the severity, both settings do the same thing and practice the same level to prevent bullying from occurring. This result is in line with the study of Donato (2013) where caregivers can prepare effective strategies to deal with bullying instances before, during, and after they occur. These strategies can be used at any point in the process. They are also able to take action to establish an atmosphere that promotes respect and is one in which bullying is neither recognized nor tolerated.

Part V. Intervention Program

Based on the thorough analysis of the data gathered and the results obtained, the researcher was able to present the significant findings of each statement of the problem of the study. The researcher comes up with an intervention that the school shall develop an intervention program for students who constantly experience and are victims of bullying and address cases or occurrences of bullying in school. Based on the summary of findings, this study developed a project titled “**SECURE (Safeguarding Education for Child-friendly, Unified, and Rescuing Environment)**”. It is being launched in response to the result of this study which found that bullying in the participating schools is slightly or notably severe. Slightly severe may mean that bullying incidents are more serious than minor cases but perhaps not the most extreme or dangerous level of severity. Essentially, it indicates that the bullying is significant enough to be concerning and requires attention, but it may not yet have escalated to the most critical or harmful levels.

Conclusions

Based on the initial findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Based on the results, it can be concluded that the Private and Public Junior High Schools have a low frequency of occurrence and low Severity of bullying incidents in terms of physical, verbal, emotional, and cyber. The Private Junior

High Schools indicated that behavior and attitude, family, and environment could sometimes contribute to cases of bullying. Whereas, for public junior high schools, the factors of behavior and attitude as well as environment seldom cause of bullying incidences, yet family is considered a factor that could contribute to incidences of bullying.

2. Considering with the research findings, there is a significant difference in the Severity of bullying cases between Private and Public Junior High Schools lead to the acceptance of the null hypothesis.
3. According to the results, the level of practices engaged by teachers and personnel to prevent the occurrence of bullying cases is high.
4. There is no significant difference in the practices to prevent the occurrence of bullying cases between Private and Public Junior High Schools lead to the acceptance of null hypothesis.
5. An intervention program was designed to address and prevent the slightly severe bullying cases in schools effectively. This program aims to establish procedures and progress monitoring of the activities and incidents regarding physical, verbal, emotional, and cyber among learners.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations are hereby offered:

1. Based on the research findings, it is imperative to enhance the capacity of educational institutions to combat bullying through comprehensive training and active involvement of the school community. Therefore, it is recommended that the Department of Education implements ongoing training for teachers, administrators, and staff on identifying, addressing, and preventing bullying. This training should emphasize recognizing the signs of bullying and appropriate intervention strategies. Additionally, schools should actively involve parents in anti-bullying initiatives through seminars, meetings, and regular communication, educating them on how family dynamics can contribute to bullying and ways they can support their children.
2. Given the evidence presented in the research, it is evident that peer support systems can significantly enhance students' emotional well-being and resilience. The school may still establish peer support groups where students can discuss issues related to bullying and support each other in a supervised environment.
3. Effectively addressing bullying is essential for maintaining a safe and supportive educational environment that enables every student to succeed academically and

socially. To this end, the school may implement a system of continuous reporting for bullying incidents to encourage students to come forward without fear of retaliation. Furthermore, the school administrator should consistently support seminars and workshops for both teachers and students to enhance and sustain bullying prevention practices within the schools.

4. In light of the study's findings, it is clear that implementing proactive and ongoing measures is crucial for effectively mitigating bullying in schools. The school administrators, along with the guidance designates/coordinators and teachers, may establish a routine schedule for reviewing and updating anti-bullying policies to ensure they reflect current best practices and address any emerging issues. Additionally, a well-developed intervention program can be used to address the bullying issue comprehensively.
5. Given the insights gained from the study, it is evident that further exploration into the degrees of bullying is necessary. Future researchers may conduct in-depth qualitative studies, including interviews, focus groups, and case studies, to gain a comprehensive understanding of personal experiences, context, responses, and outcomes related to slightly severe bullying.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study adhered to the research ethics of anonymity, consent, and beneficence. The research ensured that the data gathered were secured and observed with the utmost consideration of data privacy. No personal information provided by the respondents was divulged in the study. In addition, the teachers who provided the data of learners were given a copy of the consent form to ensure they were aware of their participation. The researcher explained in full detail the process of data gathering and assured that the data shall be treated with the utmost confidentiality. The teachers were also given the option to withdraw their participation if they felt there was a need for them to do so. Finally, the researcher informed the respondents that no benefits shall be provided to the respondents but the data they will be providing shall be helpful for the realizations and completion of the study.

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